

Correlation of VBG and ABG in Critically Ill Patients Admitted in Pediatric Intensive Care Unit in a Tertiary Care HospitalNishigandha Joshi¹, Sushma Save², Santosh Shimpiger³^{1,2,3}Department of Paediatrics, T.N.M.C and B.Y.L Nair Charitable Hospital, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Arterial blood gases (ABG) are technically more difficult to obtain, more painful, and expensive. They are associated with hazards like bleeding, arterial spasm, and thrombosis. Performing a Venous blood gas (VBG) rather than an ABG is particularly convenient in the intensive care unit since many patients have a central venous catheter from which venous blood can be quickly and easily obtained.

Objectives: The primary objective was to correlate venous pH and pCO₂ to arterial pH and pCO₂ in critically ill patients in the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU). The secondary objective was to study the accuracy of VBG for the diagnosis of acid-base balance in children admitted to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) at a tertiary care hospital.

Methods: In a prospective interventional study, 85 children admitted to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) in whom clinicians had advised ABG were recruited. ABG and VBG were obtained from the same patient at an interval of 5-10 minutes. ABG and VBG reports were later compared. The mean difference was studied by Paired t-test. The correlation of the values was tested by the Karl Pearson correlation test. Bland Altman's method was used to study the agreement.

Results: In 85 patients, the majority of the subjects belonged to <1 yrs (57.6%), with a male preponderance (46 males). The majority of the cases had respiratory system involvement. Pneumonia cases were 61.8%. The mean difference for pH between VBG and ABG was -0.01 with a Pearson correlation of 0.92. The mean difference for pCO₂ between VBG and ABG was -5.32 mm Hg with a Pearson correlation of 0.97. Points in the Bland Altman were uniformly scattered between the lines of agreement which suggested good agreement and correlation between arterial and venous pH and pCO₂.

Conclusion: Venous pH and pCO₂ showed a significant correlation and agreement with arterial pH and pCO₂. Venous pH and pCO₂ showed a significant correlation and agreement with arterial pH and pCO₂. Thus venous pH and pCO₂ estimation is an acceptable substitute for arterial measurement and may reduce the risks of complications both for patients and health workers.

Keywords: Arterial blood gas, Venous blood gas, pH, pCO₂.

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Introduction

Identification of a patient's arterial pH, pCO₂, and pO₂ is critical for diagnostic and therapeutic purposes. [1]. It has been demonstrated to be the most frequently ordered test in the Intensive Care Unit [2], Although used to evaluate many respiratory and metabolic conditions, ABG analysis is not without drawbacks [2]. ABGs are technically more difficult to obtain, more painful, and expensive. They are associated with hazards like bleeding, arterial spasm, and thrombosis [1]. The risks increase with repeated arterial punctures, especially in children with small arteries [3]. Healthcare staff is exposed to an increased risk of needle stick injuries and blood-borne infection. Venous blood sampling may be a useful alternative to ABG sampling, obviating the need for arterial puncture. [2]. VBGs

are obtained from the venous system along with other blood work. [1] Performing a VBG rather than an ABG is particularly convenient in the intensive care unit, since many patients have a central venous catheter from which venous blood can be quickly and easily obtained [3] This has resulted in a worldwide trend towards lesser invasive diagnostic method like VBG. [1] Many years, clinicians have been looking for alternatives to ABG sampling in both children and adults, and studies have investigated arterial and venous blood gas samples and the correlation between the values. [3] Recently, studies have demonstrated that there was an excellent correlation between venous pH and arterial pH and venous pCO₂ and arterial pCO₂. There have been studies published on the correlation be-

tween arterial and venous blood gases in adults. However, many of these studies have concentrated only on the adult population and their role in children with critical illness has not been evaluated. Despite existing studies, questions remain regarding the use of venous blood gas analysis instead of arterial blood gas analysis in the population of critically ill patients admitted to Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU). [3] Hence, we embarked on a study to compare venous pH and pCO₂ to arterial pH and pCO₂ in critically ill patients in PICU. Our aim was to correlate venous pH and pCO₂ to arterial pH and pCO₂ in critically ill patients in Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU).

Material and Methods

This prospective interventional over a period of 18 months in a Pediatric Intensive Care Unit study of a tertiary care Institution after obtaining approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee. The study enrolled all patients admitted to the PICU aged 29 days to 12 years whom the clinician had advised ABG. Patients who had a low platelet count that is less than 50,000, severe coagulopathy, were on anticoagulation therapy with warfarin, heparin, and direct thrombin inhibitors, and had local infection were excluded.

At the time of admission, the patient's clinical details were recorded in a prefix proforma consisting of age, sex, diagnosis duration of patients in PICU, and value of arterial blood gas obtained from each patient enrolled in the study was recorded. Informed consent was taken from every parent and in addition to consent, verbal assent was taken for patients above 7yrs as soon as the patient stabilized.

After informed consent, ABG and VBG samples were obtained as temporally close to each other as possible. The resident posted in the PICU was informed to collect VBG as a part of other blood work. ABG was obtained from the radial artery. Reports of ABG and VBG were later compared. The mean difference was studied by Paired t-test. The correlation of the values was tested by the Karl Pearson correlation test. Bland Altman's method

was used to study the agreement.

Results

Among 85 participants, the majority of the study subjects were in the age group of <1 year (57.6%), followed by ≥6 years (30.6%) and 1-5 years (11.8%) as shown in Table 1 and Figure 1. There were 46 males and 39 females as shown in Table 2 and Figure 2. In our study, most cases had respiratory system involvement as shown in Figure 3. Pneumonia cases accounted for 61.18%, cases of sepsis were (14.12) %, Bronchiolitis (7.06%) Acute gastroenteritis (4.71%), Congenital heart diseases (3.53%), Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome (2.35%), Hyper reactive Airway disease (2.35%), Bronchiectasis (1.18%) Diabetic Ketoacidosis (1.18%), Right sided Pleural effusion (1.18%), Congestive Cardiac Failure (1.18%). Table 3 shows the descriptive statistics of arterial and venous blood gas values of the two parameters measured (pH and pCO₂).

Mean arterial and venous pH were 7.31 and 7.32 respectively, as shown in Figure 4. Mean arterial and venous pCO₂ were 44.73 and 50.05 respectively, as shown in Figure 5. In our study, the mean difference in pH between VBG and ABG was 0.01 as shown in Table 4 with a Pearson correlation of 0.92 as shown in Table 5 and Figure 6 (scatter plot). The mean difference for pCO₂ between VBG and ABG was 5.32 mm Hg as shown in Table 4 with a Pearson correlation of 0.97 as shown in Table 6 and Figure 7 (scatter plot). A significant correlation was found between the ABG pH and VBG pH, ($r=0.923$; $P<0.05$). Similarly, pCO₂ measured by ABG and VBG method was also found significant correlation ($r=0.977$; $P<0.05$).

The mean difference for pH between VBG and ABG was -0.01 with a Pearson correlation of 0.92. The mean difference for pCO₂ between VBG and ABG was -5.32 mm Hg with a Pearson correlation of 0.97. Points in the Bland Altman were uniformly scattered between the lines of agreement which suggested good agreement and correlation between arterial and venous pH and pCO₂ in our study shown in Figures 8 and 9 respectively.

Table 1: Distribution of study population based on age groups

		Number	Percentage (%)
Age groups	<1 year	49	57.6
	1-5 years	10	11.8
	≥6 years	26	30.6
	Total	85	100.0

Table 2: Distribution of study population based on gender

		Number	Percentage (%)
Gender	Males	46	54.1
	Females	39	45.9
	Total	85	100.0

Figure 1: Distribution of study population based on age groups

Figure 2: Distribution of study population based on gender

Figure 3: Distribution of study population based on diagnosis in Pediatric Intensive Care Unit

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of arterial and venous blood gas values of the two parameters measured pH and PCO₂ (n=85)

Summary Statistics	ABG-pH	VBG-pH	ABG-PCO ₂	VBG-PCO ₂
Sample size	85.00	85.00	85.00	85.00
Arithmetic mean	7.31	7.32	44.73	50.05
95% CI for the mean	7.30 to 7.34	7.29 to 7.33	48.31 to 51.801	42.921 to 46.531
Variance	0.01	0.01	65.52	69.71
Standard deviation	0.08	0.07	8.09	8.35
Standard error of the mean	0.01	0.01	0.88	0.91

Figure 4: Mean arterial and venous pH

Figure 5: Mean arterial and venous pCO2

Table 4: Mean Difference (95% Confidence Interval [CI]), and Correlation of pH and pCO2 Comparing Venous and Arterial Blood Samples for 85 Study Participants.

Parameter	Mean difference	SD of differences	Standard error of mean difference	95% CI of difference	t Statistic	Degrees of Freedom (DF)	Two-tailed probability
VBG - ABG pH	0.01	0.03	0.00	-0.01581 to -0.002543	-2.75	84.00	P = 0.0073
VBG - ABG PCO2	5.32	1.76	0.19	-5.7028 to -4.9442	-27.91	84.00	P < 0.0001

Figure 6: Scatter plot showing strong correlation between arterial and venous pH of the study population

Figure 7: Scatter plot showing strong correlation between arterial and venous pCO2 levels of the study population

Table 5: Correlation between arterial pH and venous pH in the study population

	Correlation Coefficient	P value
Arterial pH vs Venous pH	0.923	<0.05

Table 6: Correlation between arterial pCO2 and venous pCO2 in the study population

	Correlation Coefficient	P value
Arterial PCO2 vs Venous PCO2	0.97	<0.05

Figure 8: Bland Altman plot showing good agreement between arterial and venous pH of the study population

Figure 9: Bland Altman plot showing good agreement between arterial and venous pCO₂ of the study population

Discussion

ABG analysis has been a cornerstone in the management of acutely ill patients with presumed acid-base imbalances. Analysis of pH, bicarbonate, and base excess is an important component of the assessment of the clinical status and progress of critically ill patients. [2]. In our prospective cohort study done in the PICU 85 patients were enrolled. The majority of the study subjects were in the age group of <1 year (57.6%), followed by ≥ 6 years (30.6%) and 1-5 years (11.8%).

In our study, most cases had respiratory system involvement of which cases of pneumonia were maximum similar to the study by Yildizdas et al. [3] where the majority of the cases were having respiratory system involvement.

In a prospective cohort study by Zeserson et al. [1] on the correlation of Venous blood gas with arterial blood gas in 156 patients, the mean difference for pH between VBG and ABG was 0.03 with a Pearson correlation of 0.94. The mean difference for PCO₂ between VBG and ABG was 4.8 mm Hg with a Pearson correlation of 0.93. In their study pH and PCO₂ on VBG analysis correlated with pH and PCO₂ on ABG analysis. Similar results were found in our study where the mean difference in pH between VBG and ABG was 0.01. Similarly, a significant correlation was found between PCO₂ measured by ABG and VBG methods. Similar results were obtained in a prospective study by Awasthi et al. [2] which was done on 45 patients. The mean difference between arterial and venous pH was 0.05 and between arterial and venous PCO₂ was 5.58 mmHg. The correlation coeffi-

cients between arterial and venous pH and PCO₂ were 0.95 and 0.83 and a significant correlation was found between arterial pH, PCO₂, and venous pH and PCO₂. Similar results were found in studies by Malatesha et al [4] and Kelly et al [5].

Results found in a prospective study in a tertiary care hospital by Khan et al. [6] showed the mean difference between arterial and venous pH was 0.02 units and for PCO₂ was 5.32 mmHg. The correlation coefficients between arterial and venous pH and PCO₂ were 0.93 and 0.89 respectively which were also similar to our study.

A cross-sectional study by Esmaeili and et al. [7] assessed the correlation and agreement between arterial and venous blood gas in 100 patients undergoing elective Coronary Artery Bypass Graft (CABG) surgery. The mean difference between arterial and venous values pH and PCO₂ were 0.04 and -6.59 mmHg. Similar results were found in a study on patients with acute exacerbation of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease by Bingheng et al [8]

In another prospective observational study by Bijapur et al. [9] in India, the mean difference between arterial and venous values for pH and PCO₂ was 0.04 units and 5.84 mmHg. The correlation coefficients for pH and PCO₂ were 0.79 and 0.83 respectively. The venous PCO₂ was higher than the arterial PCO₂. Similar results were found in our study. The correlation coefficient values ranged from being negatively correlated (-1), to uncorrelated (0), to positively correlated (+1) (0 is no correlation, 0.3 is weakly positive, 0.5 is moderately positive, 0.8 is strongly positive and +1 is perfectly posi-

tive). The study showed a good correlation between arterial pH and PCO₂ and venous pH and PCO₂ and that venous blood gas could be an acceptable substitute for arterial measurements in many clinical settings encountered in PICU obviating the need for repeated arterial sampling. Similar results were found in our study.

Similar results were also found in another cross-sectional observational study by Adhikari et al. [10], a total of 50 samples were analyzed. The mean differences between arterial and venous values for pH and PCO₂ were 0.02 units, 2.37 mmHg, and the correlation coefficients between arterial and venous parameters were 0.96 and 0.88. Venous pH and PCO₂ showed a high correlation with respective arterial values

Points in the Bland Altman were uniformly scattered between the lines of agreement which suggested good agreement and correlation between arterial and venous pH and PCO₂ in our study. Similar results were found in a prospective observational study by Bijapur et al [9] in India where the Bland-Altman method was used to study the agreement between arterial and venous blood values and points were uniformly scattered between the lines of agreement which suggested good agreement and correlation between arterial and venous pH and PCO₂.

In the cross-sectional study by Esmailvand et al. [7], correlation and agreement between arterial and venous blood gas in 100 patients undergoing elective Coronary Artery Bypass Graft, Bland Altman method was used to study the agreement between arterial and venous blood values. The Bland-Altman analysis showed excellent agreement between these variables.

In the scatter plot, a strong correlation existed since all the points lay nearby along the straight line called the line of equality. There was a significant correlation between the two measurements of pH (Karl Pearson $r=0.923$; $P<0.05$) and PCO₂ (Karl Pearson $r=0.977$; $P<0.05$). Similar results were found in a study in a tertiary care hospital in Katmandu, a strong correlation was found between arterial pH and venous pH with a Karl Pearson coefficient of 0.96 and between arterial and PCO₂ with a Karl Pearson coefficient of 0.94. The limitation of our study was the small sample size.

Conclusion

Our study emphasizes that venous pH and PCO₂ showed a significant correlation and agreement with arterial pH and PCO₂. Thus venous pH and PCO₂ estimation is an acceptable substitute for arterial measurement and may reduce the risks of complications both for patients and health workers.

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